

ICB-UMA at BioCreative IX 2025 Track 3 - ToxHabits: Named Entity Recognition for Detection of Substance Use and Abuse in Clinical Texts.

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Abstract

The consumption and abuse of psychoactive substances constitute a global public health concern, exerting a profound impact not only on individual quality of life but also on collective well-being. Consequently, the precise identification and comprehensive characterization of consumption patterns are essential for a more thorough understanding of this phenomenon as well as for the effective design and implementation of preventive strategies. Clinical texts serve as a key source for obtaining detailed and accurate information regarding these patterns. Nevertheless, access to such documents is particularly challenging due to the inherent sensitivity and confidentiality of the clinical data they contain. The scarcity of these clinical records, and thus the lack of sufficiently high-quality annotated corpora, significantly constrains the development and evaluation of solutions based on advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques. In response to this limitation, shared task initiatives such as ToxHabits become particularly relevant, as they provide novel data sources specifically designed to foster methodological and technological advances in the detection and characterization of toxic habits. This paper presents the approach developed by the Computational Intelligence in Biomedicine research group at the University of Malaga. The proposed methodology is designed to maximize both precision and coverage in the detection of substance consumption patterns through NLP. To this end, solutions based on BIO (Begin-Inside-Outside) tagging and span-based models have been implemented, leveraging the capabilities of pre-trained BERT-like language models. Additionally, ensemble strategies employing soft-voting have been explored with the aim of further enhancing predictive robustness and overall performance. The results obtained demonstrate outstanding performance in both evaluated subtasks, achieving F1-scores of 0.84 and 0.75, respectively.

Keywords

Named Entity Recognition, BIO tagging, Span-based, Ensemble models

1. Introduction

Automatic information extraction is one of the core tasks in NLP, with substantial impact on applications such as entity and relation retrieval or automatic summarization. This process becomes especially relevant in the current context of progressive digitalization, where the volume of textual data is growing exponentially, both in general domains and in highly specialized sectors. In the healthcare field, the implementation of electronic health records (EHRs) has led to the massive accumulation of unstructured clinical information originating from medical notes, diagnostic reports, and diverse hospital documentation. As the amount of available textual information increases across both general and specialized domains, the need for robust techniques capable of efficiently identifying, extracting, and structuring information becomes ever more pressing.

Despite the significant progress achieved in recent years, NLP continues to face challenges arising from the variability and complexity of language—particularly in the medical domain, where abbreviations and terminological heterogeneity are prevalent. Moreover, the lack of formal structure and stylistic variation demands a greater availability of data; however, the sensitivity of such data restricts access, resulting in few-shot or even zero-shot learning scenarios.

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Given the scarcity of high-quality annotations, initiatives such as shared tasks are particularly relevant, as they offer standardized and accessible resources that help to partially overcome these limitations. In this regard, ToxHabits focuses on the detection and characterization of psychoactive substance consumption and abuse patterns within the clinical domain. This task has been divided into two subtasks: ToxNER and ToxUse. The first subtask aims to identify explicit mentions of toxic habits—namely alcohol, tobacco, and other substances. In contrast, ToxUse focuses on classifying the use status associated with each mention—active use, past use, absence of use, or insufficient information.

In this work, both subtasks are addressed through the development and evaluation of two complementary approaches. On one hand, a sequential BIO tagging scheme—widely used in named entity recognition (NER) tasks—has been implemented. On the other hand, a span-based modeling approach has been explored, wherein entities are detected via the direct prediction of text spans. For both approaches, we have leveraged the capabilities of pre-trained BERT-like language models. To enhance robustness and improve the overall predictive performance, both approaches have been integrated using ensemble techniques, including majority vote and soft-voting. This strategy combines the strengths of each model and enables a more effective adaptation to the inherent complexity of clinical texts.

2. Related Work

NER is one of the principal tasks within automatic information extraction. It involves the identification and categorization of text sequences corresponding to instances of interest, such as persons, diseases, procedures, or pharmaceuticals. This task has undergone substantial development since its inception. Initially, extraction was carried out using rule-based approaches [1]. This procedure consisted of defining rules intended to cover all possible ways in which a given text sequence of interest might appear. However, this method was highly labor-intensive and failed to address all potential cases due to the inherent complexity of language [2].

With the advent of digital transformation and the emergence of EHRs, the availability of annotated data increased significantly. As a result, most solutions migrated from rule-based methods to supervised machine learning algorithms. In [3], Zhou and collaborators developed a system based on Support Vector Machines, demonstrating its effectiveness in generalization and adaptation across different domains. Simultaneously, Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) gained prominence due to their ability to model sequences and exploit contextual dependencies. Kuo et al.[4] proposed an architecture that integrated bidirectional sentence analysis with the use of CRFs, capturing both preceding and succeeding dependencies for each term, thereby optimizing the segmentation and classification of biomedical entities. Furthermore, Tsai et al.[5] advanced the specialization of CRF-based models with NERBio, incorporating novel features and preprocessing techniques, such as the combination of linguistic properties and numerical normalization, which significantly improved the performance of NER in biomedical texts.

The emergence of deep learning led to its integration into the biomedical domain. Notably, models based on recurrent neural networks, such as BiLSTM-CRF architectures [6], established the methodological foundations for the transformative breakthrough brought by Transformers [7]. This architecture marked a paradigm shift in NLP by introducing the attention mechanism [8], which enables efficient modeling of long-range dependencies and complex contextual relationships. The outstanding performance of Transformer-based foundation models across numerous fields has driven the emergence of multiple variants. It has also motivated adaptation strategies tailored to specialized domains, often implemented through continual pretraining. Among these are models such as ClinicalBERT [9], BioBERT [10], PubMedBERT [11], or BETO-Galén [12].

Currently, generative large language models (Gen LLMs) represent the cutting edge in natural language processing, facilitating the resolution of NER and information extraction tasks in zero-shot and few-shot settings. Nevertheless, their application in biomedical contexts still faces challenges related to the generation of spurious or unverifiable responses. Among the most advanced strategies for mitigating these limitations are retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) approaches [13], advanced

prompt engineering, and the use of chain-of-thought reasoning [14], all of which have shown a significant impact in enhancing the robustness and reliability of these systems in specialized domains.

Finally, it is important to note that the vast majority of these developments and evaluations have been conducted in English, which restricts their applicability and generalization to less-resourced languages such as Spanish. The scarcity of resources and annotated corpora in Spanish remains a significant obstacle to advancing biomedical NLP in this language. In this context, recent initiatives such as DisTEMIST, MedProcNER, SympTEMIST, and, more recently, ToxHabits [15], are crucial for driving the development, evaluation, and adoption of advanced technologies for clinical entity recognition and normalization in Spanish.

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Corpus description

The ToxHabits shared task comprises two subtasks for information extraction from Spanish clinical texts: ToxNER, which focuses on identifying mentions of toxic habits, and ToxUse, which is dedicated to classifying the use status associated with each mention. For both subtasks, the dataset consists of 1,199 Spanish clinical texts, with 7,592 annotations for ToxNER and 9,528 for ToxUse. During preprocessing, documents without annotations were removed—31 in ToxNER and 190 in ToxUse—as well as overlapping annotations—122 in ToxNER and 949 in ToxUse.

After this curation process, the distribution of annotations per document was analyzed to ensure that the training and validation splits preserved the proportion of labels within each partition. Table 1 presents the final distribution of documents and annotations for ToxNER, including the breakdown for each of the four main labels, while Table 2 summarizes the allocation by annotation type for ToxUse. In both cases, the proportion of labels remains similar between the training and validation splits, thereby contributing to a balanced evaluation of system performance.

Table 1

Distribution of annotations and documents by split and label in the ToxNER subtask.

Split	Documents	Annotations	Drug	Alcohol	Tobacco	Cannabis
Train	817	5104	3117 (61.07%)	874 (17.12%)	584 (11.44%)	529 (10.36%)
Val	351	2366	1492 (63.06%)	381 (16.10%)	243 (10.27%)	250 (10.57%)

Table 2

Distribution of annotations and documents by split and label in the ToxUse subtask.

Split	Documents	Annotations	Type	Frequency	Amount	Duration	Method	History
Train	706	5999	2512 (41.87%)	937 (15.62%)	909 (15.15%)	893 (14.89%)	478 (7.97%)	270 (4.50%)
Val	303	2580	1082 (41.94%)	423 (16.40%)	383 (14.84%)	384 (14.88%)	186 (7.21%)	122 (4.73%)

3.2. Named Entity Recognition from clinical texts

The methodology employed in this study relies on two main approaches for NER: sequential tagging based on the BIO scheme and span-based extraction models. First, a series of models were fine-tuned using the BIO tagging scheme, in which each token is classified according to whether it marks the beginning, the inside, or the outside of an entity. For example, in the sentence “*She is a compulsive smoker*”, the sequence of labels would be: *She* (O), *is* (O), *a* (O), *compulsive* (B-Tobacco), *smoker* (I-Tobacco). For this approach, two Spanish pre-trained encoder-based language models were trained: PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es [16] and PlanTL-GOB-ES/bsc-bio-ehres [17]. Both are RoBERTa-based models pre-trained on a biomedical-clinical corpora in Spanish

collected from several sources. To maximize the available context for the model, each document was segmented into sentences, and, using a greedy strategy, as many consecutive sentences as possible were grouped within a single window, without exceeding the maximum allowable length and thus avoiding the truncation of relevant information. To enable a rigorous comparison with previous state-of-the-art approaches, both tokenizers were also used to train two BiLSTM-CRF models—widely considered as the previous standard for biomedical NER in Spanish—allowing direct performance evaluation under identical tokenization and pre-processing conditions.

As an alternative, the training of span-based models¹ was explored. Rather than tagging each token individually, these models evaluate all possible combinations of consecutive words within a window defined by a maximum length. The model assigns a probability to each of these spans indicating whether it corresponds to an entity. As with the BIO approach, both models were fine-tuned for the NER task. For instance, given the text “*She is a compulsive smoker*”, the model analyzes all possible segments such as (*She, is*), (*She, is, a*), and so forth, up to the maximum allowed length. In this way, it is capable of identifying that the span “*compulsive smoker*” constitutes a mention of type Tobacco.

In both approaches, model behavior was evaluated by systematically varying the learning rate (from 1×10^{-5} to 5×10^{-5}) and batch size (from 1 to 32). In the case of span-based models, the maximum span length parameter was also explored (values of 5 and 10), while higher values were avoided to prevent a significant imbalance in the proportion of negative samples.

4. Discussion and Results

To ensure an accurate evaluation, BIO-based models and span-based models were considered independently, employing token-level metrics for BIO and entity-level metrics for span-based models. All BiLSTM-CRF baselines were also implemented using the BIO tagging scheme, allowing for a direct and fair comparison with transformer-based BIO models and span-based approaches. Table 3 presents the average results—mean \pm standard deviation—of precision, recall, F1-score, and average runtime—training execution time—obtained for all models.

It can be observed that, in subtask1, BIO models exhibit greater variability in results and achieve significantly lower scores compared to span-based models. In particular, BiLSTM-CRF models, which represent the previous state-of-the-art for biomedical NER, yield the lowest F1-scores and the largest standard deviations among all BIO-based approaches, indicating less stable and robust performance. For example, the best BIO model reaches an F1-score of 0.713 ± 0.031 , whereas SpanMarker models exceed 0.80 in F1-score with much lower deviation, indicating greater robustness and generalization capacity in the identification of complete mentions—the mean and standard deviation are derived from multiple training runs performed with varying learning rates and batch sizes. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that BIO models yield even lower results in subtask1—which would be expected to be simpler—compared to span-based models in subtask2, which presents greater complexity.

Lastly, it is important to highlight the difference in computational requirements between both approaches: the average inference time per run for span-based models is approximately three to four times higher than that of BIO models, which entails greater computational cost and increased demand for resources during training and deployment.

Following the validation analysis, the best configuration for each model was selected for each subtask, and a combination strategy based on soft-voting and ensemble was designed. Specifically, the following five submissions were made: (i) span-based model initialized with `roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es`, (ii) span-based model initialized with `bsc-bio-ehr-es`, (iii) ensemble of both span-based models using majority voting and soft-voting, (iv) ensemble of both BIO models, and (v) ensemble combining the BIO models and the two span-based models, leveraging the combination of predictions for broader coverage.

Finally, Table 4 shows that the different model combinations achieve outstanding results, with F1-scores above 0.8 for ToxNER and close to 0.75 for ToxUse.

¹SpanMarker: <https://github.com/tomaarsen/SpanMarkerNER>

Table 3

Results obtained on the validation set for the ToxNER and ToxUse subtasks. *Note: BIO models were evaluated at the token level, while span-based models were evaluated at the entity level.*

Tags	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Runtime
ToxNER				
BIO-roberta-base-bio-cli-es	0.710 ± 0.044	0.645 ± 0.045	0.676 ± 0.042	00:32:26
BIO-bsc-bio-ehr-es	0.743 ± 0.036	0.686 ± 0.032	0.713 ± 0.031	00:23:22
BiLSTM-CRF-roberta-base-bio-cli-es	0.750 ± 0.070	0.532 ± 0.191	0.594 ± 0.145	01:46:53
BiLSTM-CRF-bsc-bio-ehr-es	0.724 ± 0.043	0.524 ± 0.193	0.582 ± 0.149	01:50:23
<u>Span-based-roberta-base-bio-cli-es</u>	<u>0.772 ± 0.028</u>	<u>0.840 ± 0.014</u>	<u>0.804 ± 0.015</u>	<u>01:47:12</u>
Span-based-bsc-bio-ehr-es	0.780 ± 0.007	0.834 ± 0.021	0.806 ± 0.007	01:48:24
ToxUse				
BIO-roberta-base-bio-cli-es	0.753 ± 0.013	0.748 ± 0.022	0.750 ± 0.014	00:38:41
BIO-bsc-bio-ehr-es	0.743 ± 0.015	0.756 ± 0.022	0.749 ± 0.013	00:21:02
BiLSTM-CRF-roberta-base-bio-cli-es	0.637 ± 0.110	0.355 ± 0.187	0.416 ± 0.168	01:39:20
BiLSTM-CRF-bsc-bio-ehr-es	0.640 ± 0.128	0.371 ± 0.198	0.424 ± 0.183	01:53:08
<u>Span-based-roberta-base-bio-cli-es</u>	<u>0.760 ± 0.028</u>	<u>0.772 ± 0.027</u>	<u>0.766 ± 0.009</u>	<u>01:11:25</u>
Span-based-bsc-bio-ehr-es	0.767 ± 0.009	0.769 ± 0.022	0.768 ± 0.013	01:22:24

Table 4

Results obtained for the ToxNER and ToxUse subtasks. *Note: The highest value for each metric is highlighted in bold, while the second highest is underlined.*

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score
ToxNER			
Span-based (roberta-base-bio-cli-es)	<u>0.82</u>	0.80	0.81
Span-based (bsc-bio-ehr-es)	0.83	0.85	0.84
Span-based ensemble	0.78	<u>0.87</u>	<u>0.82</u>
BIO Ensemble	0.76	0.84	0.80
BIO-Span-based Ensemble	0.72	0.91	0.80
ToxUse			
Span-based (roberta-base-bio-cli-es)	0.76	0.72	<u>0.74</u>
Span-based (bsc-bio-ehr-es)	0.61	0.84	0.71
Span-based ensemble	<u>0.73</u>	0.77	0.75
BIO Ensemble	0.65	<u>0.80</u>	0.72
BIO-Span-based Ensemble	0.61	0.84	0.71

5. Conclusions

In this study, we have explored two alternative approaches to the NER task aimed at detecting health-related toxic habits, including not only the identification of the specific habit but also the recognition of its history and duration. In particular, we compared the traditional BIO tagging scheme and the more recent span-based methodology. The results obtained in both subtasks demonstrate very high performance, with F1-scores exceeding 0.8 in ToxNER and approaching 0.75 in ToxUse. This highlights the potential of the evaluated models and the combination strategies employed. However, a greater variability has been observed in the results obtained by the BIO tagging approach, as evidenced by a higher standard deviation. In contrast, span-based models have proven to be significantly more computationally demanding, with inference times reaching three to four times those of the BIO tagging models.

Among the most promising future directions is the generation of new synthetic data as a data augmentation strategy, leveraging the clear structure and guidelines provided by the ToxHabits organizers,

which would help reinforce the robustness of the models in scenarios with fewer annotated data. Moreover, the exploration of Gen LLMs for entity recognition is particularly appealing, especially when incorporating advanced techniques such as chain-of-thought and prompt engineering, which are emerging at the forefront of natural language processing. In particular, designing prompts that incorporate CoT reasoning based on explicit rules and entity definitions drawn from the task descriptions and annotation guidelines can guide the model through more structured reasoning steps, ultimately enhancing its consistency and interpretability. This approach enables the encoding of domain-specific knowledge directly into the prompting process, helping the model better align with the annotation criteria. These lines of research open new possibilities for further improving the performance and adaptability of NLP systems in the multilingual clinical domain.

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